

Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials in Barangay Adlay as Mandated by Republic Act No. 10742

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Abstract

The Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) is the youth council in the Philippines that serves as a platform for young individuals to participate in local governance and advocate for the needs and interests of the youth in their communities. The study aimed to assess the perception of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials in Brgy. Adlay as mandated by Republic Act No. 10742. The study anchored the essential instrument to Rule 2, Section 8 of the Rules and Regulations Implementing Republic Act No. 10742, otherwise known as the Sangguniang Kabataan Reform Act of 2015. The study was conducted in Barangay Adlay, Carrascal, Surigao Del Sur, during the second semester of the academic year 2021-2022. The study administered three groups of participants: Elected Barangay Officials (10), Sangguniang Kabataan Officials (5), and Katipunan ng Kabataan (102). Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution, Mean and Standard Deviation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to treat the data. The majority were male; aged between 25-30 years old and College Level. Based on the study's findings, the overall performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) in Barangay Adlay received a positive rating, with Barangay Officials perceiving it most favorably, while the Katipunan ng Kabataan had a lower perception rating. However, there was a significant variance in perception among the participant groups, indicating a need for improved community engagement and communication. The study recommends continued training and support for SK officials, guidance from Barangay Officials, regular consultations, transparency in transactions, and active participation from the Katipunan ng Kabataan to enhance the SK's performance and engagement in local governance.

Keywords: Sangguniang kabataan, katipunan ng kabataan, barangay officials, republic act of 2015, performance, Philippines

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The word "Youth" became word-of-mouth in every aspect ever since Gat. Jose P. Rizal pinpointed that the "Youth is the hope of the nation." From then, complex schemes were initiated by different institutions to advocate for youth empowerment. Given that fact, governments started to include youth to be an advocates in politics.

In the Philippines, the youth has been pigeonholed to a role in nation-building. Likewise, in the Philippines, the country has an exemplary reform structure in allowing the youth to participate, influence, and lead the public. In connection, the nation's inclusion of youth in governance is shown through the creation and operation of "Sangguniang Kabataan," which is formerly known as "Kabataang Barangay" (Village Youth) by Presidential Decree 648 under Marcos's regimen. It has undergone a reform called Republic Act no. 10742, otherwise known as the "Sangguniang Kabataan Reform Act of 2016 due to major incompetencies in the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan officials." In this reform act, the duties and responsibilities of the elected Sangguniang Kabataan Officials are well-stipulated as to the discharge and exercise of these roles in the community and for the benefit of the Katipunan ng Kabataan. The duties and responsibilities of the Sangguniang Kabataan in the reform act are under Chapter 2, Section 8 of the mentioned reform act. This is to ensure that the powers and functions of the Sangguniang Kabataan are vividly comprehensive and systematic.

Incorporating the divided judgment viewed by the Katipunan ng Kabataan in Barangay Adlay. The performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan was perceived with both positive and negative implications and criticisms.

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On that account, this year, the Sangguniang Kabataan of Adlay received backlash from the Katipunan ng Kabataan via social media. In support of this, on November 13, 2021, a post went viral on Facebook authored by Bravura of Isabella which was originally posted on April 20, 2018. The post contained the expected performances and skills of the aspiring Sangguniang Kabataan Officials. The post reached some of the Katipunan ng Kabataan of Brgy. Adlay which were Facebook users. The issue snowballed when Molinar shared the post with a negative caption about the current Sangguniang Kabataan Officials. The caption of Molinar raged at the chairperson of the Sangguniang Kabataan. The argument they started attracted some of the Katipunan ng Kabataan of Brgy. Adlay to speak up. This led to the question of the capabilities and performances of the current Sangguniang Kabataan Officials in Brgy. Adlay.

With this considerable problem, the researchers were prompted to assess the perceived performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials of Brgy. Adlay subsuming the powers and functions of a Sangguniang Kabataan official as mandated and stipulated under Republic Act No. 10742, "SANGGUNYANG KABATAAN REFORM ACT OF 2016." Likewise, it aimed to propose recommendations that would enhance the leadership performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials.

1.2 Objectives

The study aimed to assess the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials of Brgy. Adlay. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Educational Attainment; and,
 - 1.3 Sex?
2. What is the assessment on the indicators of Sangguniang Kabataan as assessed by:
 - 2.1. Barangay Officials;
 - 2.2. Sangguniang Kabataan Officials; and,
 - 2.3. Katipunan ng Kabataan (Youth)?
3. Is there any significant variance in the results of the perception of the performances of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials?
4. Is there any significant variance in the results of the perception of the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials when grouped according to their profile?
5. Based on the results of the study, what recommendation may be proposed?

1.3 Literature Review

The participation of the youth in nation-building is vital as the state recognizes the potential of the young minds in shaping good governance. [1] acknowledged the role of the youth by asserting that the participation of youth refers to a process whereby the youth can engage and influence. It may also refer to an outcome where the young people had a chance to contribute to a process. It is also supported by Maguire (2007), who coined that the youth are tomorrow's leaders, parents, professionals, and workers and today's assets. Properly supported and given the right opportunities, girls and boys, young women and young men can play a significant part in lifting themselves, their families, and communities out of poverty. On the contrary, according to Youth Political Participation or YPP (2017), it negates that young people are often excluded or overlooked as political leaders. Politics is typically regarded as a space for politically experienced men, and while women are often disadvantaged in accumulating experience to run for office, young people are systematically marginalized because of their young ages, limited opportunities, and projected lack of experience. The claim was later supported by Maranon II (2018), asserting that researchers are proposing that the eligibility must exclude the ages 15-17 years old. Accordingly, highlighted in his report, "Legislators reasoned that those 15 years of age but under 18 are still minors under the law, and thus ineligible to enter into contracts. This is due to the youth's political immaturity, which was also supported by other studies.

On the other hand, in an observation initiated by Balane (2015), he pinpointed that everywhere in the country, young people are making the world a better place, making their voices heard for gender equality, poor urban development, sustainable environment, and other relevant issues. He also added that the youth are getting more creative in pushing for important reforms in the government by doing art protests. Incorporating the judgment of Commonwealth (2015) highlighted the fact that young people are empowered when they have or can create choices

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in life, are aware of the implications of those choices, make an informed decision freely, take action based on that decision and accept responsibility for the consequences of those actions.

Finally, under the UNRC (2011), it encompasses a message that Youths have the right to express their views and to give their opinions. It is undeniably true that the youth have a vital role in nation-building and establishing a future that is progressive and neutral.

Sangguniang Kabataan (SK)

The performance of a Sangguniang Kabataan is perceived to have an important role in nation-building. This is an engagement overruled by the State to provide the youth inclusivity in good governance. Before the history of the devolution of power, during the presidency of late President Ferdinand E. Marcos, the Kabataang Barangay (KB) was created. The aim of the creation and operation of the organization is to encourage youths in rural areas to participate in real governance. In an article written by Buenaventura, he added that the KB was formed to counter the growing influence of the Kabataang Makabayan, a left-leaning youth movement that fought the government during Marcos' presidency as well as the growing number of young activists who went underground. On the other hand, it was abolished years after the late President Corazon C. Aquino became the president of the Philippines. In place of the Kabataang Barangay, it was created and re-established through the Local Government Code of 1991 paired with a new change which is the Sangguniang Kabataan concept. More so, Sangguniang Kabataan councils are elected by the members of the Katipunan ng Kabataan in elections conducted by the Commission on Elections (COMELEC). Republic Act No. 10742 makes the effectivity on promotion of Youth Participation possible and effective. This validates the idea of

In the testimony of Gorospe (2018) in his article entitled, "Moral Challenges of SK election," he pinpointed that if the requirements for aspiring youth politicians would be measured by their skills in leadership and management, their constituencies would, at the very least, have lesser headaches in choosing the best among the worst. Likewise, he added that for so many years, it had been made evident that government officials lack intelligence, or if not, principles. Up to now, there have been no initiatives to reevaluate our legal criteria for public servants.

According to Vivas (2015) that there was a general observation that the Sangguniang Kabataan, under its current structure, had lost its effectiveness in advancing the democratic ideals in service-oriented youth leadership. The community had already observed that the young leaders duly elected are being inefficient in their own respective offices. On the other hand, the ineffectiveness of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan may be just a lack of engagement that was due to a lack of trust between youth and adult community members, in the government (Winkler n.d.). Nevertheless, Arnold (2008), pinpointed those evaluations of existing programs and showed that the most successful ones began with youth that was outstanding and motivated to be active, who were then trained and given access to existing research and best practices, and culminated with Youth- Adult integration. The claim of Arnold was supported by Zeldin (2012) by exemplifying that intergenerational partnership is often key in enabling youth to be successful because youth often lack all the requisite skills and know-how to carry out activities and programs. Moreover, the National Youth Commission or NYC (2015) predetermined that the Sangguniang Kabataan has an inherently limited role as "the sole policy-making coordinating body of all youth-related institution, programs, projects and activities of the government."

Despite the controversies that questioned the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan, the CDO Youth Development Council (2014) supported the fact that the Sangguniang Kabataan played a huge impact on young people in making local governments effective, and it is felt across the nation and spreading to more cities, shattering away old political chains like elitism, patronage, and cynicism. As a result, there is an increased likelihood of obtaining proper skills, personality, and character which are crucial variables for fostering good leadership. One important quality of the youth, when they select their leaders, is that they look for competency, goal setting, a generation of new ideas, and examines the relationship between age and personality traits (Edwards, 1994; Kress, 2006). Likewise, the Sangguniang Kabataan ultimately leads the youth to a democratic, effective, self-reliant, progressive, and most of all god abiding and morally upright sector in Philippine society (Katipunan ng Mga Kabataan & Sangguniang Kabataan Federation, 2001).

Powers and Functions of Sangguniang Kabataan

After being dormant for roughly five years, the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK), or youth council has not only returned but also been reformed through Republic Act Number 10742. It is clear under Rule 2, Section 3, of the Republic Act No. 10742 the powers and functions of Sangguniang Kabataan. In relation, these powers and functions

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are promulgate resolutions necessary to carry out the objectives of the youth in the barangay, in accordance with applicable provisions of the Code; Initiate programs designed to enhance the social, political, economic, cultural, and intellectual, moral, spiritual and physical development of the members; Hold fundraising activities, the proceeds of which shall be tax-exempt and shall accrue to the Sangguniang Kabataan general fund; Create such bodies or committees necessary to effectively carry out its programs and activities; Submit annual end-of-term reports to the Sangguniang Barangay on their projects and activities; Consult and coordinate with all youth organizations in the barangay for policy formulation and program implementation; Coordinate with the Presidential Council for Youths (PCYA) and other National Government Agencies (NGA) concerned for the implementation of youth development projects and programs at the national level; and Exercise such other powers and perform such other duties and functions as the Sangguniang Barangay may determine or delegate or as may be prescribed by law or ordinance.

In the study by Peregrino (2014) entitled "Sangguniang Kabataan: Showground for Youth Participation in the Case of Malabon City," the findings and results of SK Leaders' performance in the conduct of their powers and functions were given a grade of 3.50, which falls between neutral judgments to being effective. In the same study, ratings of the Projects conducted by the SK in the selected Barangays, the respondents gave an average grade of 2.9411, which corresponds to a neutral verdict. Likewise, according to Cuenco and Aranas (2016), the inhabitants of Anahawan, Southern Leyte, were quite satisfied with the SK's legislative performance (3.62 rating on a scale of 1 to 4). One notable study was pioneered by Caldo (2015) who dared to link good governance to the competency, of the Barangay officials and the Sangguniang Barangay to which the Sangguniang Kabataan belongs. He assessed the competency measures of the said officials and the findings revealed that the Punong Barangay and Sangguniang barangay members have strong confidence that they are competent in performing their duties and functions; but this goes in contradiction to the response of the selected participants who are residents in the locality, who said that they are uncertain to the performance of their barangay officials and Sangguniang Barangay wherein Sangguniang Kabataan is included. Moreover, a study was conducted and initiated by the United Nations Children Economic Fund - Manila and the Department of Interior and Local Government to study the status, impacts, and accomplishments of the SK. The study reveals that though the SK has both positive and negative images on its official, its function was not practiced to its fullest. SK is weak, particularly in legislation, reports, and consultation with its constituents (UNICEF, 2007; DILG, 2007). Accordingly, in the study conducted by Concepcion, Tancinco (2016) entitled "The Youth Leaders and Their Contributions to The Selected Barangays in The Municipality of Naval, Biliran, Philippines," the results of the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan in connection to their mandated Powers and functions, they concluded that there were more projects of youth leaders (SK Officials) were implemented than the programs and related youth activities. Dumbrique (2014) also discovered that Vigan City's SK received a high rating in terms of duty completion by their citizens and barangay Chairman in local governance and community development, and their responsibilities and impact.

On the other hand, the Youth Attributes, Participation, and Service Providers (YAPS) study NYC conducted in 2004 asserts that the youth believe that the SK should create role models for them and organize sports and youth activities. With it, the 2001 Katipunan ng Kabataan and Sangguniang Kabataan Constitutions and By-Laws state that they will assume a role in national development and governance and as an active supporter and participating partner of the government in formulating programs.

Katipunan ng Kabataan (Youth)

According to Article II, Section 13 of the 1987 Constitution, "The State recognizes the vital role of the youth in nation-building and shall promote and protect their physical, moral, spiritual, intellectual and social well-being. It shall inculcate in the youth patriotism nationalism, and encourage their involvement in public and civic affairs." In pursuit of the constitution, Katipunan ng Kabataan (KK) was created through the Local Government Code of 1991 (Republic Act 7160) which provides an opportunity for young people to directly participate in local governance. In the Katipunan ng Kabataan, active participation is a question for the local authorities.

In accordance to Labajo, Dublin, and Soriano (2020) in their qualitative analysis entitled, "A Qualitative Synthesis of Children's Narratives from Consultations on Civic Participation and Governance," exemplify that during the pandemic crisis, children can access information about COVID-19 and, albeit a lesser extent, public announcements provided by their barangays and LGUs. In addition, Lagbas (2015), highlighted that the strategic plan for economic development must be deliberated and participated creatively by the leadership of the youth. As supported by UNRC (2011), it revealed that the youth have the right to express their views and give their opinions. In the Philippine setting, to make the role of the youth more centralized and focused, the word "youth" was exemplified as those persons whose ages

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range from fifteen (15) to thirty (30) years old as defined and stipulated in the Republic Act No. 8044 and also highlighted on Section 3 of the Rules and Regulations Implementing Republic Act No. 10742. The programmed age disaggregation of the youth is accordingly subdivided into three parts: 15-17 (child youth), 18-24 (core youth), and 25-30 (adult youth).

Synthesis of the Review. The statements and relevant ideas gathered from the readings were related to the study. The review of related literature gave the researchers important and relevant information and ideas that provided beneficial insights and implications on the Perceptions of the Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as mandated by a ruling law. As shown in the readings above, the comparison and contrast of ideas were systematically emphasized in line with the course on which the study was focused. The information that the researchers explored in their research was the Perception of the Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as mandated by the Powers and Functions under Republic Act 10742. The main objective of the study was to assess the perception of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan of Adlay. Secondly, this study targeted to determine the significant difference in the results of the assessed perceptions of the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan Official, and the significant difference in the assessment of the perception of the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan when grouped according to participants' profiles: age, sex, and highest educational attainment.

2. METHODS

This study made use of a descriptive-evaluative research design utilizing a survey assessment tool. The descriptive design would describe the evaluation of the Katipunan ng Kabataan in line with the Sangguniang Kabataan's powers and functions. According to Ary, "Descriptive research studies are designed to obtain the nature of the situation as it exists at the time of the study. Thus, descriptive research aimed to describe what exists. Likewise, according to Villanueva (2013) that descriptive-evaluative research design seeks to carefully appraise the worthiness of a current study. The research design was the most applicable design to anchor for this study because a descriptive method will observe, describe, and document aspects of a situation as it naturally occurs. Likewise, this study only needs to evaluate and collect information without the need to manipulate variables like age, sex, and highest educational attainment from the respondents.

The participants for the study were the Katipunan ng Kabataan (Youth), Sangguniang Kabataan Officials (SK), and the Barangay Officials of the respective Local Government of Adlay. Accordingly, the selection of the Katipunan ng Kabataan and Sangguniang Kabataan Officials was based on the legible qualifications anchored on Republic Act No. 10742. The researchers anchored the questionnaire to Section 8, Chapter 2 of Republic Act No. 10742. In this section, the Powers and Functions of the Sangguniang Kabataan were highlighted and adopted from Republic Act No. 10742. These paragraphs were used as indicators for the rating-questionnaire style. The researchers formulated a two-part questionnaire. Part 1 contains the profile of the participants; Part 2 of the questionnaire contains all about the assessment of the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan. The assessment was analyzed and interpreted utilizing statistical tools such as Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution, Mean and Standard Deviation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.

Profile of the Participants

Profile Variables		
	f (n=10)	%
Barangay Officials		
Sex		
Male	8	80.00
Female	2	20.00
Highest Educational Attainment		
High School Graduate	1	10.00
College Level	6	60.00
College Graduate	3	30.00

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	f (n=5)	%
SK Officials		
Age		
18-24 years old	5	100.00
Sex		
Male	3	60.00
Female	2	40.00
Highest Educational Attainment		
College Level	4	80.00
College Graduate	1	20.00
Katipunan ng Kabataan		
Age		
15-17 years old	22	21.57
18-24 years old	28	27.45
25-30 years old	52	50.98
Sex		
Male	62	60.78
Female	40	39.22
Highest Educational Attainment		
High School Level	11	10.78
High School Graduate	4	3.92
College Level	70	68.63
College Graduate	17	16.67

Table 1 presents the profile of participants of the Barangay Officials, Sangguniang Kabataan Officials, and Katipunan ng Kabataan in Barangay Adlay. It was calculated and determined by their age, sex, and highest educational attainment.

The table provided information in terms of sex. The results showed that out of ten (10) Barangay Officials, eight (8) or 80% are male participants, and two (2) or 20% are female participants. While, out of five (5) Sangguniang Kabataan Officials, three (3), or 60% are male participants, and two (2), or 40% are female participants. Moreover, out of one hundred two (102) Katipunan ng Kabataan, sixty-two (62) or 60.78% are male participants, and forty (40), or 39.22% are female participants. This means to say that in all three groups of participants, the majority of them are male. As to age, all five (5) or 100% of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials are 18-24 years of age. While, out of one hundred two (102) Katipunan ng Kabataan, fifty-two (52) or 50.98% are 25-30 years old, twenty-eight (28), or 27.45% are 18-24 years old, and twenty-two (22) or 21.57% are 15-17 years old. It shows that most of the Katipunan ng Kabataan participants were between 25-30 years old. According to UNESCO, the definition of "youth" as used by a particular Member State, is based on the definition also given in the African Charter where "youth" means "every person between the ages of 15 and 35 years." On the other hand, the word "youth" was categorized as those persons whose ages range from fifteen (15) to thirty (30) years old as defined and stipulated in Republic Act No. 8044 and also highlighted in Section 3 of the Rules and Regulations Implementing Republic Act No. 10742. The programmed age disaggregation of the youth is accordingly subdivided into three parts: 15-17 (child youth), 18-24 (core youth), and 25-30 (adult youth).

As to the highest educational attainment, it can be noticed from the table that out of ten (10) Barangay Officials, six (6) or 60% are at the College Level, three (3) or 30% are College Graduates, and one (1) or 10% is a High School Graduate. Meaning, that most of them are at the college level. Meanwhile, out of five (5) Sangguniang Kabataan, four (4), or 80% are at College Level and one (1) or 20% is a College Graduate. Meaning, that only one among the participants was able to graduate college. While out of one hundred two (120) Katipunan ng Kabataan, seventy (70) or 68.63% are at College Level, seventeen (17) or 16.67% are College Graduates, eleven (11) or 10.78% are in Highschool Level, four (4) or 3.92% are High School Graduates. Meaning, that most of them were at the College Level. However, among the three groups of participants in terms of Highest Educational Attainment, none was in Elementary Level and Elementary Graduate. According to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) 2011, as published by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)

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Institute for Statistics (2012, p. 20, paragraph 81) that "The educational attainment of an individual is defined as the highest ISCED level completed by the individual. For operational purposes, educational attainment is usually measured concerning the highest education program completed, which is typically certified by a recognized qualification."

Table 2. *The Assessment of the Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as Perceived by the Barangay Officials*

Indicators	<u>M</u>	<u>SD</u>	<u>VI</u>	<u>QD</u>
Powers and Functions of Sangguniang Kabataan (as assessed by the Brgy. Officials)				
1. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay, within three months after winning the position, consults the youth to formulate a three-year plan or project. <i>(Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay, sa loob ng tatlong buwan matapos manalo sa posisyon, ay kumunsulta sa kabataan upang bumuo ng isang tatlong taong plano o proyekto.)</i>	2.90	0.88	A	VS
2. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay promulgates Resolutions necessary to carry out the objectives of the youth in the barangay. <i>(Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay nagsusulong ng mga Resolusyon na kinakailangan upang maisakatuparan ang mga layunin ng kabataan sa barangay).</i>	3.30	0.48	SA	O
3. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay initiates and implements, in coordination with any institution or organization in conducting programs, and projects aimed to promote the general welfare, development and empowerment of youth. <i>(Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay nagsisimula at nagpapatupad, sa koordinasyon sa anumang institusyon o samahan sa pagsasagawa ng mga programa, at mga proyekto na naglalayong itaguyod ang pangkalahatang kapakanan, kaunlaran at pagpapalakas ng kabataan).</i>	3.30	0.48	SA	O
4. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay holds fund-raising activities. <i>(Ang sangguniang kabataan council ng brgy. Adlay ay nagsasagawa ng mga aktibidad sa pangangalap ng pondo).</i>	3.60	0.52	SA	O
5. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay creates committees necessary to effectively carry out its programs and activities. <i>(Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay lumilikha ng mga komite na kinakailangan upang mabisang maisagawa ang mga programa at aktibidad nito).</i>	3.40	0.52	SA	O
6. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay submits the annual and end-of-term program accomplishments and financial reports to the Sangguniang Barangay <i>(Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay isinasumite ang taunang at pagtatapos ng mga tagumpay sa programa at mga ulat sa pananalapi sa Sangguniang Barangay).</i>	2.90	0.88	A	VS
7. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay partners with the Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) in planning projects and programs of specific advocacies like good governance, climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction and resiliency, youth employment and livelihood, health and anti-drug abuse, gender sensitivity, and sports development. <i>(Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay kasosyo ang Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) sa</i>	3.50	0.53	SA	O

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<i>pagpapalano ng mga proyekto at programa ng mga tiyak na adbokasiya tulad ng mabuting pamamahala, pagbagay sa pagbabago ng klima, pagbawas sa peligro ng kalamidad at katatagan, pagtatrabaho at kabuhayan ng kabataan, pang-aabuso sa kalusugan at laban sa droga, pagkasensitibo ng kasarian, at palakasan kaunlaran).</i>					
8.	The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay conducts youth profiling, establish, maintain and update a database of youth in the barangay. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay nagsasagawa ng profiling ng kabataan, nagtatatag, nagpapanatili at nag-a-update ng isang database ng kabataan sa barangay.</i>)	2.70	0.95	A	VS
9.	The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay assists in the establishment and registration of youth organizations and youth serving organizations in the barangay. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay tumutulong sa pagtatatag at pagpaparehistro ng mga samahan ng kabataan at mga organisasyong nagsisilbi ng kabataan sa barangay.</i>)	3.00	0.47	A	VS
10.	The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay adopts and implements a policy on full public disclosure of all its transactions and documents involving public interest. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay pinagtibay at ipinatutupad ang isang patakaran sa buong pagsisiwalat sa publiko ng lahat ng mga transaksyon at dokumento na kinasasangkutan ng interes ng publiko.</i>)	2.70	0.82	A	VS
Average:		3.13	0.65	A	VS

Legend: *M*- Mean, *SD*- Standard Deviation, *VI*- Verbal Interpretation, *QD*- Qualitative Description

Table 2 presents the assessment of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by the Barangay Officials. On Indicator 4, "The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay holds fund-raising activities" obtained the highest mean ($M= 3.60$) and the standard deviation of ($SD=0.54$) with the verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree with a qualitative description of Outstanding. This only shows that the Barangay Officials, as superior officials of the Sangguniang Kabataan, were aware of and commended the activities like fun-raising administered by the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials. The result goes contradictory to the interpretation of Conception, Tancinco (2016), concluded in their study that there were more projects administered by the Sangguniang Kabataan of Naval, Biliran than compared implementing programs and youth activities.

On the other hand, as shown from the table that both Indicators 8 and 10, "The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay conducts youth profiling, establish, maintain and update a database of youth in the barangay," and, "The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay adopts and implements a policy on full public disclosure of all its transactions and documents involving public interest," both scored the lowest mean ($M=2.70$) with verbal interpretation as Agree and qualitative description of Very Satisfactory. This reveals that though the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials obtained a Very Satisfactory in both indicators, still, the Brgy. Officials perceived that these indicators need more improvement as to youth profiling, establishing and maintaining the youth database, as well as the implementation of public disclosure of all transactions. In the study conducted by the United Nations Children Economic Fund- Manila and the DILG, they revealed that the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials were perceived in both positive and negative images wherein its function was not practiced to the fullest. Thus, the Sangguniang Kabataan was seen as weak in reports, legislation, and consultation.

Table 3. *The Assessment of the Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as Perceived by the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials*

Indicators	<u>M</u>	<u>SD</u>	<u>VI</u>	<u>QD</u>
Powers and Functions of Sangguniang Kabataan (as assessed by the SK Officials)				
1.The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay, within three months after winning the position, consults the youth to formulate a three-year plan or project. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay, sa loob ng tatlong buwan matapos manalo sa posisyon, ay kumunsulta sa kabataan upang bumuo ng isang tatlong taong plano o proyekto.</i>)	3.60	0.55	SA	O
2. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay promulgates Resolutions necessary to carry out the objectives of the youth in the barangay. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay nagsusulong ng mga Resolusyon na kinakailangan upang maisakatuparan ang mga layunin ng kabataan sa barangay.</i>)	3.40	0.55	SA	O

3. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay initiates and implements, in coordination with any institution or organization in conducting programs, and projects aimed to promote the general welfare, development and empowerment of youth. (Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay nagsisimula at nagpapatupad, sa koordinasyon sa anumang institusyon o samahan sa pagsasagawa ng mga programa, at mga proyekto na naglalayong itaguyod ang pangkalahatang kapakanan, kaunlaran at pagpapalakas ng kabataan)	3.40	0.55	SA	O
4. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay holds fund-raising activities. (Ang sangguniang kabataan council ng brgy. nagsasagawa ng mga aktibidad sa pangangalap ng pondo si adlay).	2.40	0.55	D	S
5. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay creates committees necessary to effectively carry out its programs and activities. (Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay lumilikha ng mga komite na kinakailangan upang mabisang maisagawa ang mga programa at aktibidad nito).	2.20	0.84	D	S
6. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay submits the annual and end-of-term program accomplishments and financial reports to the Sangguniang Barangay and present the same during the KK assembly (Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay isinasumite ang taunang at pagtatapos ng mga tagumpay sa programa at mga ulat sa pananalapi sa Sangguniang Barangay at nagpapakita ng pareho sa pagpupulong ng KK).	3.00	0.00	A	VS
7. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay partners with the Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) in planning projects and programs of specific advocacies like good governance, climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction and resiliency, youth employment and livelihood, health and anti-drug abuse, gender sensitivity, and sports development. (Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay kasosyo ang Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) sa pagpapalano ng mga proyekto at programa ng mga tiyak na adbokasiya tulad ng mabuting pamamahala, pagbagay sa pagbabago ng klima, pagbawas sa peligro ng kalamidad at katatagan, pagtatrabaho at kabuhayan ng kabataan, pang-aabuso sa kalusugan at laban sa droga, pagkasensitibo ng kasarian, at palakasan kaunlaran).	3.00	0.00	A	VS
8. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay conducts youth profiling, establish, maintain and update a database of youth in the barangay. (Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay nagsasagawa ng profiling ng kabataan, nagtatatag, nagpapanatili at nag-a-update ng isang database ng kabataan sa barangay).	3.40	0.55	SA	O
9. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay assists in the establishment and registration of youth organizations and youth serving organizations in the barangay. (Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay tumutulong sa pagtatatag at pagpaparehistro ng mga samahan ng kabataan at mga organisasyong nagsisilbi ng kabataan sa barangay).	3.20	0.45	A	VS
10. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay adopts and implements a policy on full public disclosure of all its transactions and documents involving public interest. (Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay pinagtibay at ipinatutupad ang isang patakaran sa buong pagsisiwalat sa publiko ng lahat ng mga transaksyon at dokumento na kinasangkutan ng interes ng publiko).	3.00	1.00	A	VS
Average:	3.06	0.52	A	VS

Legend: *M*- Mean, *SD*- Standard Deviation, *VI*- Verbal Interpretation, *QD*- Qualitative Description

Table 3 presents the assessment of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by the Sangguniang Kabataan themselves. Accordingly, it can be observed that Indicator 1, “The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay, within three months after winning the position, consults the youth to formulate a three-year plan or project,” and got the highest mean ($M=3.60$) with the verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree and qualitative description of Outstanding. The results revealed that the Sangguniang Kabataan themselves prioritized the consultation with the Katipunan ng Kabataan in formulating a three-year plan or project. Concerning it, the Katipunan ng Kabataan and Sangguniang Kabataan Constitutions and By-Laws (2001) stated that the Sangguniang Kabataan should participate in and formulate programs and projects. In addition, in the study of Conception, Tancinco (2016), concluded that there were more projects formulated by youth leaders of the Municipality of Naval, Biliran.

On the contrary, as indicated in Table 3, Indicator 5, “The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay creates committees necessary to effectively carry out its programs and activities” got the lowest mean ($M=2.20$) with a verbal interpretation of Disagree and qualitative description of Satisfactory. This only means that the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials were creating committees to effectively execute programs and activities. Yet, they are aware that it is not very satisfactory. Following the claims of Zeldin (2012), he asserted that youth often lack all the requisite skills and how to carry out activities and programs.

Table 4. The Assessment of the Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as Perceived by the Katipunan ng Kabataan

Indicators	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>QD</i>
Powers and Functions of Sangguniang Kabataan (as perceived by the Katipunan ng Kabataan)				

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1. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay, within three months after winning the position, consults the youth to formulate a three-year plan or project. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay, sa loob ng tatlong buwan matapos manalo sa posisyon, ay kumunsulta sa kabataan upang bumuo ng isang tatlong taong plano o proyekto</i>).	2.83	0.63	A	VS
2. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay promulgates Resolutions necessary to carry out the objectives of the youth in the barangay. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay nagsusulong ng mga Resolusyon na kinakailangan upang maisakatuparan ang mga layunin ng kabataan sa barangay</i>).	2.80	0.51	A	VS
3. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay initiates and implements, in coordination with any institution or organization in conducting programs, and projects aimed to promote the general welfare, development and empowerment of youth. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay nagsisimula at nagpapatupad, sa koordinasyon sa anumang institusyon o samahan sa pagsasagawa ng mga programa, at mga proyekto na naglalayong itaguyod ang pangkalahatang kapakanan, kaunlaran at pagpapalakas ng kabataan</i>).	2.71	0.64	A	VS
4. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay holds fund-raising activities. (<i>Ang sangguniang kabataan council ng brgy. Adlay ay nagsasagawa ng mga aktibidad sa pangangalap ng pondo</i>).	2.54	0.64	A	VS
5. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay creates committees necessary to effectively carry out its programs and activities. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay lumilikha ng mga komite na kinakailangan upang mabisang maisagawa ang mga programa at aktibidad nito</i>).	2.63	0.67	A	VS
6. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay submits the annual and end-of-term program accomplishments and financial reports to the Sangguniang Barangay and present the same during the KK assembly (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay isinasumite ang taunang at pagtatapos ng mga tagumpay sa programa at mga ulat sa pananalapi sa Sangguniang Barangay at nagpapakita ng pareho sa pagpupulong ng KK</i>).	2.54	0.64	A	VS
7. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay partners with the Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) in planning projects and programs of specific advocacies like good governance, climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction and resiliency, youth employment and livelihood, health and anti-drug abuse, gender sensitivity, and sports development. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay kasosyo ang Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) sa pagpapalano ng mga proyekto at programa ng mga tiyak na adbokasiya tulad ng mabuting pamamahala, pagbagay sa pagbabago ng klima, pagbawas sa peligro ng kalamidad at katatagan, pagtatrabaho at kabuhayan ng kabataan, pang-aabuso sa kalusugan at laban sa droga, pagkasensitibo ng kasarian, at palakasan kaunlaran</i>).	2.61	0.62	A	VS
8. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay conducts youth profiling, establish, maintain and update a database of youth in the barangay. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay nagsasagawa ng profiling ng kabataan, nagtatatag, nagpapanatili at nag-a-update ng isang database ng kabataan sa barangay</i>).	2.54	0.64	A	VS
9. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay assists in the establishment and registration of youth organizations and youth serving organizations in the barangay. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay tumutulong sa pagtatatag at pagpaparehistro ng mga samahan ng kabataan at mga organisasyong nagsisilbi ng kabataan sa barangay</i>).	2.56	0.59	A	VS
10. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay adopts and implements a policy on full public disclosure of all its transactions and documents involving public interest. (<i>Ang Sangguniang Kabataan Council ng Brgy. Adlay ay pinagtibay at ipinatutupad ang isang patakaran sa buong pagsisiwalat sa publiko ng lahat ng mga transaksyon at dokumento na kinasasangkutan ng interes ng publiko</i>).	2.51	0.63	A	VS
Average:	2.60	0.62	A	VS

Legend: **M**- Mean, **SD**- Standard Deviation, **VI**- Verbal Interpretation, **QD**- Qualitative Description

Table 4 presents the assessment of the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by the Katipunan ng Kabataan. As shown from Table Statement 1, "The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay, within three months after winning the position, consults the youth to formulate a three-year plan or project" obtained the highest mean (M=2.83) and standard deviation (SD=0.63), with a verbal interpretation of Agree and qualitative description of Often. This goes to say that the Sangguniang Kabataan's consultation and formulation of a three-year plan, within three months after winning the position for the benefit of the whole Katipunan ng Kabataan was organized well and often.

According to the study conducted by Malaluan, Baja, Carandang, Vergara, and Tamayo entitled, "Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials as Mandated by the Local Government Code of 1991 that even though all were positively assessed, the powers and functions of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials such as

consultation and coordination with all youth organizations in the barangay for policy formulation and program implementation weighted a mean of 2.98 with a verbal interpretation of Good.

However, as shown in Table 4, particularly Statement 10, "The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay adopts and implements a policy on full public disclosure of all its transactions and documents involving public interest," it got the lowest mean (M=2.51) and standard deviation (SD=0.63) with the verbal interpretation of Agree and qualitative description of Often. Meaning, that the Sangguniang Kabataan, despite garnering the lowest point in assessment as to the implementation of the policy that holds public disclosure of all transactions and documents, still, was able to manage the implementation as part of their duties being public servants.

In addition, as cited from the study conducted and initiated by the United Nations Children Economic Fund - Manila and the Department of Interior and Local Government on the study concerning the status, impacts, and accomplishments of the SK, it revealed that though the SK has both positive and negative images on its officials, its function was not being practiced to its fullest. SK is weak, particularly in legislation, reports, consultation with its constituents, and public disclosure of transactions (UNICEF, 2007; DILG, 2007). According to Concepcion & Tancinco (2016) in the study entitled, "The Youth Leaders and Their Contributions to the Selected Barangays in the Municipality of Naval, Biliran, Philippines," the results of the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan in connection to their mandated Powers and functions concluded that there were more projects of youth leaders (SK Officials) which were implemented than the programs and related youth activities.

Table 5. Significant Variance on the Results of the Assessment in the Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as Perceived by the Three Groups of Participants

Indicators	Responses of the Barangay Officials				Responses of the Sangguniang Kabataan				Responses of the Katipunan ng Kabataan			
	M	SD	VI	QD	M	SD	VI	QD	M	SD	VI	QD
1. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay, within three months after winning the position, consults the youth to formulate a three-year plan or project.	2.90	0.88	A	VS	3.60	0.55	SA	O	2.83	0.63	A	VS
2. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay promulgates Resolutions necessary to carry out the objectives of the youth in the barangay.	3.30	0.48	SA	O	3.40	0.55	SA	O	2.80	0.51	A	VS
3. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay initiates and implements, in coordination with any institution or organization in conducting programs, and projects aimed to promote the general welfare, development, and empowerment of youth.	3.30	0.48	SA	O	3.40	0.55	SA	O	2.71	0.64	A	VS
4. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay holds fund-raising activities.	3.60	0.52	SA	O	2.40	0.55	D	S	2.54	0.64	A	VS
5. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay creates committees necessary to effectively carry out its programs and activities.	3.40	0.52	SA	O	2.20	0.84	D	S	2.63	0.67	A	VS
6. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay submits the annual and end-of-term program accomplishments and financial reports to the Sangguniang Barangay and presents the same during the KK assembly.	2.90	0.88	A	VS	3.00	0.00	A	VS	2.54	0.62	A	VS
7. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay partners with the Local Youth Development Council (LYDC) in planning projects and programs of specific advocacies like good governance, climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction and resiliency, youth employment and livelihood, health and anti-drug abuse, gender sensitivity, and sports development.	3.50	0.53	SA	O	3.00	0.00	A	VS	2.61	0.62	A	VS
8. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay conducts youth profiling, and establishes, maintains, and updates a database of youth in the barangay.	2.70	0.95	A	VS	3.40	0.55	SA	O	2.54	0.64	A	VS

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9. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay assists in the establishment and registration of youth organizations and youth-serving organizations in the barangay.	3.00	0.47	A	VS	3.20	0.45	A	VS	2.56	0.59	A	VS
10. The Sangguniang Kabataan Council of Brgy. Adlay adopts and implements a policy on full public disclosure of all its transactions and documents involving public interest.	2.70	0.82	A	VS	3.00	1.00	A	VS	2.51	0.63	A	VS
Average:	3.13	0.65	A	VS	3.06	0.52	A	VS	2.60	0.62	A	VS
Overall Average:	M= 2.93		SD= 0.59		VI=A		QD=VS					

Legend: **M**- Mean, **SD**- Standard Deviation, **VI**- Verbal Interpretation, **QD**- Qualitative Description

Table 5 presents the significant variance in the results of the assessment of the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by the three-group of participants. It can be observed that the responses of the Barangay Officials got the average mean (3.13) with the verbal interpretation of Agree and qualitative description of Very Satisfactory. While the responses of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials obtained an average mean (3.06) with the verbal interpretation of Agree and qualitatively description of Very Satisfactory. Moreover, the responses of the Katipunan ng Kabataa got the average mean (2.60) with the verbal interpretation of Agree and qualitative description of Very Satisfactory.

Furthermore, the overall mean as assessed by the three-grouped of participants gained an average mean (2.93) with the verbal interpretation of Agree and qualitative description of Very Satisfactory. The overall average mean (3.13) of Brgy. Officials with the verbal interpretation Agree and qualitative description Very Satisfactory obtained the highest mean among the three. In contrast, the overall average mean (2.60) of the Katipunan ng Kabataan with a verbal interpretation Agree and qualitatively description Very Satisfactory gained the lowest mean among the three. This implies that Brgy. Officials were more likely updated and therefore very satisfied with the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials as compared to the Katipunan ng Kabataan. For the reason that the Brgy. Officials and Sangguniang Kabataan Officials are together in one location and establishment. Moreover, the results in the assessment of the performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by the three-group of participants got the same very satisfactory rating in all the ten indicators presented.

According to a study by Cuenco and Aranas (2016), the results revealed that the community of Anawan, Southern Leyte, they were quite satisfied with the Sangguniang Kabataan's legislative performance. Moreover, in the study of Peregrino (2014), the findings and results of Sangguniang Kabataan Leader's performance in the conduct of their powers and functions were given a grade of 3.50 which falls into neutral judgments of being effective.

Table 6.

Significant Variance on the Assessment of the Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan as Perceived by the Three-group of Participants.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	Decision
Powers and Functions (three groups)	3.26	2	1.63	11.55	2.72E-05	Reject H ₀

Table 6 presents the significant difference in the assessments of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by the three-group of participants. The table above shows that there is a significant difference in the assessments of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by the three-group of participants. It can be observed that there is no sufficient basis to accept the null hypothesis. It implies that the decision on the null hypothesis should be rejected because it obtained lower than 0.05. This explains that the significant variance in the assessment was the cause of a lack of engagement and proper communication between the participants in the community.

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Accordingly, the lack of engagement was due to a lack of trust between youth and adult community members, in the government (Winkler n.d.). Ineffective communication has been cited as the greatest barrier to effective youth-adult relationships in community engagement (Handy, Rodgers, and Schwieterman 2011). Nevertheless, according to Arnold (2008), those evaluations of existing programs showed that the most successful ones began with youth that was outstanding and motivated to be active, who were then trained and given access to existing research and best practices and culminated with Youth- Adult integration. The claim of Arnold was supported by Zeldin (2012) as he exemplified that intergenerational partnership is often key in enabling youth to be successful because youth often lack all the requisite skills and know-how to carry out activities and programs

Table 7. *Significant Variance on the Assessment of the Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan when grouped according to their Profile Variables as perceived by the Barangay Officials*

Profile	Dependent	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Sex		0.03	1	0.03	0.08	0.7791	Accept
Highest Educational Attainment	Power and Functions	0.40	2	0.20	0.70	0.5283	Accept

Table 7 presents the significant variance in the assessment of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan when grouped according to their profile variables as perceived by the Barangay Officials. The table above shows that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan when grouped according to their sex and highest educational attainment as perceived by Barangay Officials. There was a sufficient basis to accept the null hypothesis as the p-values obtained were higher than 0.05. Thus, age and the highest educational attainment were not factors in their perceptions concerning the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by the Barangay Officials in Barangay Adlay.

In line with this, in the study pioneered by Butch, Mahinay (2013) entitled “Multi-Sector Perceptions on Good Governance and Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) in Brgy. Tablon, Cagayan de Oro City” where there are 8 Barangay Officials included as participants in the study, they generally concluded that there was no significant difference on the subscales and profile as to the assessment on the Sangguniang Kabataan in Brgy. Tablon regarding good governance and performance. The exclusion of this context in the study made the profile variables of Barangay Officials nonsignificant in these types of studies.

Table 8.

Significant Variance on the Assessment of the Perceptions on the Performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan as Perceived by the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials when grouped according to their Profile Variables

Profile	Dependent	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Decision
Sex		.005	1	.005	.191	.691	Accept
Highest Educational Attainment	Power and Functions	.065	1	.065	12.741	.038	Reject H ₀

Table 8 presents the significant variance in the assessment of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by themselves when grouped according to their profile variables. The table above shows that there is no significant difference in the sex of the participants. There is no sufficient basis to accept the null hypothesis. Thus, sex was not a factor in their perceptions concerning their performance as the Sangguniang Kabataan. However, the result shows that there was a significant variance in the assessment of the Sangguniang Kabataan when grouped according to their highest educational attainment. With the p-value: of .038, it can be gleaned from the data that there is no

sufficient basis to accept the null hypothesis. Thus, the highest educational attainment could be a factor in their perceptions concerning their performance as Sangguniang Kabataan in Brgy. Adlay.

In a relevant study by Tupas (2010) entitled "Level of Knowledge on the provisions of RA 7160 Sec. 431 and Level of Performance of SK Chairpersons in the Fifth Congressional District of Iloilo", he proved that there was no significant difference in the level of knowledge and performance of the SK Chairpersons in the provisions when grouped according to profile. In a project-based study pioneered by Lobato, Andreu, Cerillo, Garcia, Maldonado, Gatell, Jauset, Gallardo, and Asenjo (2010), they concluded that sex has no significant difference in the leadership performance of 4th-year students of PMP. Likewise, in the study conducted by Sacro, and Ariate (2020) entitled "The Leadership Styles of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Chairmen in Surigao City", they concluded that there was no significant difference in the determination of the three leadership styles when grouped according to profile.

In contrast, according to the article by Marx (2007) entitled "Effects of Gender, Education, and Age upon Leaders' Use of Influence Tactics and Full Range Leadership Behaviors," significant differences were found among educational level groups for individualized consideration; those leaders who had earned an advanced degree exhibited the highest rating level in their performance. In addition, there were fewer than two groups (Age) for the dependent variable which resulted in no computed statistics.

Table 9.

Significant Variance on the Assessment of the Performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan when grouped according to their Profile Variables as perceived by the Katipunan ng Kabataan

Profile	Dependent	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Age	Power and Functions	1.28	2	0.64	2.12	0.1249	Accept
Sex		0.44	1	0.44	1.44	0.2324	Accept
Highest Educational Attainment		0.17	3	0.06	0.18	0.9101	Accept

Table 9 presents the significant variance in the assessment of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan when grouped according to their profile variables as perceived by the Katipunan ng Kabataan. The results revealed that there is no significant variance in the perceptions of the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan when grouped according to their age, sex, and highest educational attainment. With the p-value results: 0.1249, 0.2324, and 0.9101, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means to say that the profile variables on age, sex, and highest educational attainment did not have effects on the perception concerning the performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan as perceived by the Katipunan ng Kabataan in Barangay Adlay. In the study conducted by Malaluan, Baja, Carandang, and Vergara entitled "Performance of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials as Mandated by the Local Government Code of 1991" where there are 200 participants mostly composed of students or youth, they found out that there was no significant difference on the perception regarding the abolition of SK and its performance when grouped according to profile variables.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study's findings led to the following conclusions: The perceived overall performance of the Sangguniang Kabataan, as assessed by the three participant groups, received an average mean rating of 2.93, indicating agreement and qualitative assessment as "Very Satisfactory." Among the participants, Barangay Officials obtained the highest average mean of 3.13, also rated as agreement and qualitatively described as "Very Satisfactory." Conversely, the Katipunan ng Kabataan had the lowest average mean of 2.60, still rated as agreement and qualitatively described as "Very Satisfactory." Additionally, a significant variance was observed in the perception of the Sangguniang Kabataan's performance among the three participant groups, which could be attributed to a lack of community engagement and effective communication. Notably, factors such as age, sex, and highest educational attainment were found to not influence the perception of the Sangguniang Kabataan's performance. Consequently, the assessment of the Sangguniang Kabataan's performance varied when participants were grouped based on their highest educational attainment.

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Based on the study's conclusion, several recommendations were proposed. Firstly, the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) should continue to host leadership activities, training, seminars, and information drives for Sangguniang Kabataan Officials to enhance their understanding and application of the mandated powers and functions outlined in the Sangguniang Kabataan Reform Act of 2015. Secondly, the Barangay Officials of Barangay Adlay should continue to provide guidance and supervision to the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials, acting as their superiors, to ensure the proper execution of their duties and encourage their active involvement in local affairs. Additionally, the Local Government Unit (LGU) should continue to organize meetings for consultations, problem-solving, and updates specifically addressing the concerns of the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials. Furthermore, the Sangguniang Kabataan Officials of Barangay Adlay should prioritize the implementation of the powers and functions outlined in the Sangguniang Kabataan Reform Act of 2015, with a focus on promoting transparency, public disclosure of transactions, and effective dissemination of information to constituents. It is recommended that the Sangguniang Kabataan maintain an updated youth database and profiles, while also establishing committees to efficiently develop and implement programs. Lastly, the Katipunan ng Kabataan of Barangay Adlay should actively participate in activities initiated and organized by the Sangguniang Kabataan officials, particularly those related to public disclosure of transactions and documents relevant to the public interest. This participation aims to enhance awareness and foster increased engagement among the Katipunan ng Kabataan.

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